

STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF INTELLIGENCE AND THINKING IN PSYCHOLOGY.

Narkulov Xusan Ismoilovich

Teacher of the psychology department of TerDU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10250426>

Abstract. *Although the problem of psychological diagnosis of intelligence in continuing education is one of the important tasks of psychological research in our republic, the selection and implementation of important methodologies for researching problems in this direction is a long way for the researcher. it is natural to impose complex tasks. The world experience in psychodiagnostics of mental abilities and intelligence has its high and significant results.*

Key words; *Intellect, thinking, mind, mind, mental ability, S.I. Ojegov, ability, continuous education, A.Bine, diagnostics, mental tests, natural, special abilities.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА И МЫШЛЕНИЯ В ПСИХОЛОГИИ.

Аннотация. *Хотя проблема психологической диагностики интеллекта в непрерывном образовании является одной из важных задач психологических исследований в нашей республике, выбор и реализация важных методологий исследования проблем в этом направлении представляют собой долгий путь для исследователя. естественно ставить сложные задачи. Мировой опыт психодиагностики психических способностей и интеллекта имеет свои высокие и значительные результаты.*

Ключевые слова: *Интеллект, мышление, разум, ум, умственные способности, С.И. Ожегов, способности, непрерывное образование, А.Байн, диагностика, умственные тесты, природные, специальные способности.*

Introduction: According to the philosophical definition, intellect is the mind (from the Latin intellectus - mind, mind) - it is the general mental potential of a person, the level of realization of his abilities that he uses appropriately to adapt to life.

The explanatory dictionary of S. I. Ojegov gives the following definition: "mind (consciousness) is the ability to think, the intellectual beginning in a person" [Ojegov 1999: 249]. It follows that the concept of "intellect" itself is closely related to the concept of "ability". In a general sense, abilities are individual personal characteristics that are subjective conditions for the successful implementation of a certain type of activity. Although the problem of psychological diagnosis of intelligence in continuing education is one of the important tasks of psychological research in our republic, the selection and implementation of important methodologies for researching problems in this direction is a long way for the researcher. it is natural to impose complex tasks. The world experience in psychodiagnostics of mental abilities and intelligence has its high and significant results.

The study of intelligence in world psychology was carried out by the French psychologist A. Binet at the end of the 19th century. Initially, A. Bine, in cooperation with his students, developed a set of psychological mental tests to determine the level of development of children's intelligence. A. Bine's research was based on the functional psychological theory, which had a dominant position at that time, and the idea that mental development is the result of the

development of several natural innate functions prevailed. Based on this concept, A. Binet chose such questions for the test assignments, which significantly reduced the child's ability to use his previous knowledge and skills. A. Binet's success was that he reasonably proved that it is necessary to create a set of tests, specific for each age period, designed to measure the mental capabilities of different age periods. He expressed his opinion that the test should be independent of school knowledge, only then it is possible to check the level of mental development (intellect) of the child.

At the beginning of the 20th century, research on the study of intelligence was further developed. After the tests of A. Binet-Simon, a number of tests with a different form and appearance, their specific systems and new modifications of the tests of these authors appeared. As a result of the emergence of a system of tests in various forms and forms and the development of a large number of modifications of a number of tests, new researches began to be carried out. Therefore, in the 1920s, test research spread throughout the world and standardized tests appeared.

In 1921, the "Psychological Education" magazine published a debate organized by leading American psychologists on the subject of the test. When researchers were asked about the best way to explain and study intelligence, although their conceptions of intelligence were mutually exclusive, almost all of them rated test research as the most appropriate, most effective method. For example, L. Termen "Intelligence is the ability to think abstractly", E. Thorndike "intelligence is the correlation of knowledge and their support in adapting to the environment", H. Woodriss "Intelligence is the ability to acquire knowledge" they say.

Intelligence tests of foreign scientists such as Cattell, Segen, A. Binet and Simon, Stern, Thermen, Thurstone, J. Piaget, Wechsler are widely used in psychology in the diagnosis of intelligence, but nationally adapted tests of intelligence tests have not yet been created. Because of this, it is of urgent importance to develop nationalized versions of intellectual tests by studying the above mentioned intelligence tests and their psychodiagnostic possibilities.

Intelligence is one of the least studied areas of the cognitive sphere of personality. How can we explain the differences in people's ability to be creative, think logically, learn new things, etc.? Why are some people "great" and others condemned to bear the stigma of mental retardation? These questions have not yet been fully resolved, but methods of measuring intelligence are actively being developed. Currently, the diagnosis of intellectual abilities is represented by a large number of tests that allow us to determine the level of intelligence of a person, to determine the intelligence quotient (IQ).

Each of the tests is based on psychological theories and models of mind structure developed by the authors over many years. But how much information can these methods provide about the human mind, and how reliable is this information? These questions determined the relevance of studying existing methods of diagnosing the structure of human intelligence.

In psychology, there are generally two views on the nature of the mind. First, there is a single (general) factor of intellectual abilities, according to which intelligence can be evaluated as a whole. In this case, the object of research is the mental mechanisms that determine the intellectual behavior of a person, his adaptation to the surrounding reality, as well as the interaction of his inner and outer world (K. Spearman, E. Hunt, R. Sternberg, G. Yu. Eysenck). An example of the theory of the integrity of intellectual abilities is the theory of calculating the coefficient of mental development ("intellectual index" - IQ).

The second point of view about the nature of intellectual abilities assumes the existence of many independent components of intelligence (J. Gilford, M.A. Kholodnaya, L. Thurson, G. Gardner). Researchers give different classifications based on different principles.

Thinking or reasoning is considered to be the highest form of the student's creative activity, intelligence, etiquette, and conscious behavior. Creative thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for the rational and effective implementation of a large-scale creative activity of the student. In the realization of creative thinking, thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses, goals, etc. are formed in the student, and they are expressed in the mind of a person as concepts, judgments, conclusions. Creative thinking is closely related to language and speech, and they mutually require each other. For the same reason, the student is fundamentally different from other beings due to his creative thinking (communication), speech, and conscious behavior.

The problem of creative thinking and talent was widely studied by the Russian psychologist N.S. Leytes, whose research was conducted on the study of individual characteristics of students' talent. According to N.S. Leytes, the ability to give creative effort to work is the main factor of talent. N.S. Leytes evaluated thinking as a psychological characteristic of a person that creates conditions for successful performance of a specified type of activity. The ability to perform the activity and the level of success will depend on it. This definition was proven in the researches of N.S. Leytes, who concluded that: "Thinking is a characteristic of a person that is a guarantee of the possibility and level of success of an activity." N.S. Leites researched the question of the natural foundations of general creative thinking and put forward the idea that they consist of activity and self-control. Activity is a general universal internal ability to perform any activity, which is manifested depending on age. Activity and self-control are formal dynamic characteristics of an individual.

The relationship between knowledge, skills and creative development is widely studied in the work of N.S. describes the rapid and efficient accumulation of knowledge that can help solve problems. Such students are somewhat ahead of their peers in creative development. Research by A.S. Leytes emphasized the need for an individual approach in identifying and developing creative thinking. V.A. Krutestkii talks about mathematical thinking, which is a characteristic of creative activity, and first of all, he touches on a somewhat common misconception among teachers. First, mathematical thinking is considered to consist primarily of quick and accurate calculation thinking. In fact, computational thinking does not always equate to truly mathematical thinking. Second, mathematically minded students are thought to have excellent memories for remembering formulas, numbers, and numbers. However, in mathematics, quick and solid memorization of a large number of numbers, facts, numbers, and formulas is much less based on thinking. V. A. Krutestkii says that thinking about mathematics affects the character of perception of mathematical problems. Thinking students, while perceiving the problem, can immediately distinguish the indicators that are important for a certain type of the problem and the quantities that are not important for a certain type, and are not important for a specific option, but are important for this specific option.

Thinking students' thinking in the process of mathematical activity:

a) with quick and broad generalization; b) with a tendency to make complete conclusions; c) mobility of thinking processes, variety of points of view in solving problems, with easy and free transition from one creative activity to another; g) is characterized by a desire for accuracy, simplicity and rationality in solving the problem.

The memory of students with high mathematical thinking is manifested differently in relation to various elements of mathematical systems, their memory has a generalized character. Types of problems and methods of solving them, schemes of ideas, arguments and proofs are quickly remembered and firmly stored in memory. When it comes to memorizing specific information, numbers, numbers, it should be said that it is neutral in relation to mathematical thinking. Such students differ in their well-developed spatial imagination, but they may not rely on visual images when solving a number of problems. For them, logic in some sense replaces "figurativeness", they do not face difficulties when dealing with abstract schemes.

The Russian psychologist N.A. Menchinskaya researched the psychological issues of students' failure to learn in the educational process, and in her research, teaching students who do not learn in experimental groups on the basis of a special program, their thinking processes (analysis, synthesis, generalization, etc.) focused on the issue of teaching to think through and thereby improving the knowledge of students. He described his research work in this regard in his work entitled "Psychological problems of students' failure to learn". According to the author, in order to determine the reason for the lack of mastery related to the characteristics of the student's personality, it is necessary to determine the set of characteristics of the student's personality that the failure in the educational activity is related to. Despite the diversity of such characteristics, it is possible to show some of their typical aspects that can serve as a basis for dividing students into groups. In particular, when analyzing the issue of psychological characteristics of students who do not master, it is necessary to take into account how their creative activity is realized when mastering various educational subjects.

Uzbek scientists M.G. Davletshin, E. Goziev, B.R. Kadirov, Z. Nishonova, E. Usmonova, R. Sunnatova and others conducted research on the problem of creative thinking. For example, psychologist M.G. Davletshin analyzed the manifestation of technical thinking in students: "The technical thinking of students is mainly manifested in technical creativity. Research on the technical thinking of students has shown that there are different levels of technical thinking. First of all, they are reproductive and creative levels. Also, M.G. Davletshin conducted research on the structure of technical thinking and distinguished some aspects of the structure of technical talent. The author says that one of them is technical observability, and success in performing technical tasks depends on the quality of perception and the level of technical observability.

B.R. Kadirov researched the psychophysiological aspects of the professional ability of teenagers and found that many factors influence the choice of a profession: social requirements, fashion, position of the profession, family profession traditions, as well as individual thinking, interests, desires, and the individual's involvement in this or that activity. It is emphasized separately that the desire to be, as well as the level of creative thinking have an effect. The basis of B.R. Kadirov's research is the study of individual abilities that encourage teenagers to engage in certain activities. Research shows that different levels and forms of brain activity encourage an individual to engage in one or another type of activity.

E.Z.Usmonova studied the problem of emotional-motivational management of thinking in different situations and analyzed how thinking takes place in a unique way in the process of cooperation in relation to the individual situation. E.Z.Usmonova believed that one of the important aspects of studying thinking is to identify the factors affecting the effective solution of intellectual issues in the process of interpersonal interaction.

On the basis of the above, we have defined the problem of creative thinking according to the opinions of scientists and the analysis of literature as follows: creative thinking is a gift of nature, it needs education, it has the character of continuous development, and it is the general development of a person. It is considered a multifaceted individual psychological characteristic that determines the level of development and the way of thinking.

As a conclusion, the analysis of the problem allows us to justify that creative thinking is, first of all, an individual psychological characteristic, that the individual characteristics of a person cannot create sufficient conditions for his general mental development, therefore, it is necessary to use all mental capabilities to realize mental abilities.

REFERENCES

1. Sharafutdinova X.G. Aqliy qobiliyatlarning qisqa tanlov testi // Amir Temur tavalludining 660 yilligi: Respublika ilmiy-nazariy konferensiya materiallari. - Termiz: TerDU, 1996. - 178 b.
2. Sharafutdinova X.G. Aqliy qobiliyat psixokorreksiyasi // Sog'lom avlod uchun. - Toshkent, 2007. - №3. - B. 12-14.
3. Sharafutdinova X.G. Aqliy qobiliyatning qisqa tanlov testi // Maktab va hayot. - Toshkent, 2006. - №8. - B. 26-28.
4. Abdullayeva, Z. (2023). THE ROLE OF TALENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A PERSON'S COMMUNICATION STYLE. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 179-182.
5. Ismoilovna, A. Z. (2023, February). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLLARDA BILISH JARAYONLARINING RIVOJLANISHI. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 204-210).
6. Juraevna, G. D. (2022). Psychological views on the role of parents in raising children in the family. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(10), 143-147.
7. Juraevna, D. G. (2022). Preparing young boys and girls for family life. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 1513-1517.
8. Juraevna, G. D. (2021). Prevention of divorce by preparing young people for family life. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(12), 398-401.
9. GAFFOROVA, D. (2023). Provoking factors of family breakdown in modern society. *Transnational Journal of Medicine & Health*, 2(10), 3-5.
10. GAFFOROVA, D. (2023). Psychoprophylaxis of monthly conflict generating disagreements in modern society. *Young Scholar's Academic Journal*, 2(7), 5-7.